

Optimization of MOSFET behavior in Monolayer BP

Maitreyee Biswas¹, Soham Chakraborty^{1*}, Satyajit Maji¹, Pratik Patra¹

Jalpaiguri Government Engineering College, Jalpaiguri, West Bengal, 735102¹

*E-mail: sc2507@ece.jgec.ac.in

ABSTRACT:

The semiconductor industry improves transistor technology keeping the trend of shrinking transistors based on Moore's prediction keeping an eye to the IRDS (International Roadmap for Devices & System). Generally, MOSFET provides a high on-state current but fails to provide a low off-state current. Here in this paper, we investigate the optimization of dual-gate MOSFETs using black phosphorus as the channel material, focusing on the reduction of leakage current, enhancement of on-state current, and improvement of the sub threshold slope. Various parameters are examined such as doping concentrations, gate oxide thickness, high-k dielectric to enhance device performance. The results highlight the effectiveness of 6 Å thick Hafnium Oxide and 4 Å thick Aluminum Oxide as gate dielectrics for optimal electrostatic control. Though the sub threshold slope is not achieved below 100mV/dec but the scope of improving the SS is discussed here. Additionally, we identified ideal doping concentrations that ensure high carrier transport efficiency while maintaining efficient gate modulation. These findings contribute to the development of energy-efficient, high-performance electronic devices.

KEYWORDS: MOSFET, Black Phosphorus, Dual-Gate, 2D Materials, Subthreshold Slope, Low-Power Electronics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on our literature review, we have not come across any study that uses the Non-Equilibrium Greens Function (NEGF)¹ technique to improve the behaviour of MOSFETs. Our goal in this research was to keep the on-state current high while reducing the off-state current. The mechanics of ballistic transport cannot be captured by semi classical approaches that ignore the quantum influence on threshold voltage, gate capacitance, and off current. This study presents quantum mechanical transport models for ballistic n-channel MOSFETs that are computationally efficient and based on the non-equilibrium Green's function formalism (NEGF)¹. The charge distribution and current for a particular device geometry are obtained using quantum modeling techniques, which depend on a self-consistent solution of the Schrödinger and Poisson equations.

The puckered honeycomb structure of black phosphorus (BP)^{2,5} results in anisotropic electrical characteristics. This structure offers special benefits in electronic applications by allowing electrical conductivity to change according to the direction within the material. When reduced to a monolayer, its adjustable direct band gap varies from about 0.3 eV in its bulk state to about 1.5 eV. Even though BP's hole mobility is said to be greater than that of electrons, this study looks at the n-device of 12nm channel length and explores the possibilities of reducing off-current while maintaining the high on-state current within the necessary range in accordance with IRDS guidelines. Although the same doping for s and d is used here, the necessary current can be achieved by maintaining source doping higher than drain.

MOSFETs' dual gate structure is a crucial component that makes enhanced semiconductor scaling possible by improving electrostatic control, reducing short-channel effects (SCEs), and enhancing overall device performance⁶. The dual gate minimizes SCEs and lowers leakage current by offering better channel control. Geometric screening length is shortest in dual gate FET structure than other structures and hence minimum DIBL can be achieved. So, a dual gate monolayer BP nMOSFET is conceived and researched with the benefits in mind.

2. MODEL AND METHOD

We only consider the device transport along the armchair direction, as the on-state current along the zigzag transport direction is proved to be eight orders of magnitude smaller than that along the armchair direction. We perform the transport calculations within the framework of **density functional theory (DFT)** coupled with **nonequilibrium Green's function (NEGF)** method integrated in the **Atomistix ToolKit (ATK)** 2020 package. The device Green's function is considered to be G in ballistic condition:

Where I is the identity matrix & H_{px} is the device Hamiltonian matrix of the nearest neighbour tight binding basis. The self energy $\Sigma_{S,D}$ arise due to coupling to the semi-infinite source/drain contacts. Level broadening due to contact coupling is denoted by $\Gamma_{S,D}$

$$\Gamma_{S,D} = i(\Sigma_{S,D} - \Sigma_{S,D}^\dagger) \quad (1)$$

Σ^\dagger is the conjugate transpose of the self energy matrix.

The trace of the matrix $A_{S,D}$ or the spectral function relates to LDOS and the separate contribution of source and drain can be realized.

$$A_{S,D} = G \Gamma_{S,D} G^\dagger \quad (2)$$

The retarded Green's function, which contains device information, specifically the channel Hamiltonian matrix (H), determines the LDOS. In fact, it provides information of the energy states involved in the conduction process. Increasing the number of accessible energy levels in between the source and drain Fermi levels is the function of the gate voltage. A key factor in defining channel Hamiltonian and, thus, the LDOS is channel doping². As the barrier is lowered, the goal is to increase the number of carriers that are available. The higher energy states have the highest probability of transport, according to the transmission spectra, and they are not present in the energy window that is produced by the applied V_{DS} , or the difference between the source and drain Fermi levels. The gate voltage is crucial in this situation because it permits certain energy levels to occur throughout the conduction process. Higher energy states with non-zero transmission coefficients react to the electric field in the transport direction and take part in the conduction process when the barrier height is lowered, which is possible in n-MOSFETs by applying a positive gate voltage. The MOSFET's conduction process suggests that hot carriers are involved.

One of the main difficulties with MOSFETs is obtaining low off current. Black phosphorous, an anisotropic substance, is selected for two effective masses in two directions. Despite the fact that the armchair direction is selected as the propagation direction, the MOSFET structure is monolayer, which has the maximum effective mass and energy gap. Therefore, we may attain the minimal current in off condition.

Even though large effective mass channel materials effectively limit SD tunnelling, which is thought to be the primary cause of leakage current for dual gate 2D material MOSFETs, they also have a number of drawbacks.

$$C_q = q^2 \frac{mlmh}{\pi \hbar^2}, \quad (3)$$

Channel material's low and high effective masses along its two primary axes are denoted by ml and mh . Quantum capacitance (CQ) of the channel material increases with increasing effective mass and, consequently, density of states (DOS). Thus, this research investigates the factors that can change this quantum capacitance to optimize it further.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Through our exploration of MOSFET optimization, we carefully analyzed the impact of various design parameters to enhance device performance. Doping concentration is one of the main tunable varying parameters, that we can change for better desirable performance of MOSFET. This section analyses the impact of varying the source/drain(s/d) and channel(c) doping concentrations on the performance of a dual-gate MOSFET with a black phosphorus monolayer as the channel material. A drain-to-source voltage of 0.6 V is applied, and the results are evaluated based on the behavior of carrier transport and gate control. The investigation explores different combinations of doping concentrations: Source/Drain doping (s/d): 0.06, 0.1, 0.3; Channel doping (c): -0.01, -0.06, -0.08 The results are interpreted using Density of States (DOS) images, which visually represent the distribution of allowed energy states in three distinct regions of the MOSFET. The left side is the Drain region, middle part is the Channel region, and the right side is the Source region.

In the following combinations (S/D1,C3), (S/D2, C3), (S/D3, C3), (S/D3, C2): The device shows a loss of gate control. This phenomenon can be attributed to the presence of a large number of allowed energy states in the channel region, as evident from the DOS images. When there are many energy states available in the channel, carriers can occupy these states which increases the probability of tunnelling through the channel. Under these conditions, the gate loses its ability to modulate the carrier transport effectively because the energy barrier in the channel is no longer sufficient to block or control the flow of carriers.

For the doping combination (S/D1, C2): The DOS image reveals that there is no allowed energy states present within the energy window in any region of the device, including the source, channel, and drain. Without any energy states in the source and drain, carriers cannot be injected into the channel, and negligible current will flow through the device. This complete absence of energy states renders the MOSFET non-functional for this doping combination. Such a scenario is undesirable.

For the doping combination (S/D2, C2): The DOS image indicates that the channel region has a significantly high energy barrier. This high barrier height makes it difficult for carriers to overcome and pass through the channel. Electrons generally occupy lower energy states, and only small numbers of electrons have sufficient energy to surpass this barrier.

The limited number of electrons capable of overcoming the barrier results in reducing electron concentration which causes lowering of current density. Consequently, the output current is also low, making this combination unsuitable for optimal device performance.

For the doping combinations (S/D1, C1) & (S/D2, C1): The absence of allowed energy states in the channel ensures that no tunnelling occurs, as there are no intermediate energy states for carriers to occupy during their transport. This results in excellent gate control, as the gate can effectively regulate the flow of carriers. Moreover, the presence of sufficient energy states in the source and drain regions ensures efficient injection and collection of carriers, leading to optimal current flow. This configuration strikes the right balance between gate control and carrier transport, making it the most favorable combination for device performance.

Table 1. Conversion of doping concentration from e/atom to atom/cm²

	Doping Concentration (electrons/atom)	Doping Concentration (atoms/cm ²)
Channel Doping Concentration-1(C1)	-0.01	1.76 x 10 ¹¹ (P type doping)
Channel Doping Concentration-2 (C2)	-0.06	1.06 x 10 ¹² (P type doping)
Channel Doping Concentration-3 (C-3)	-0.08	1.41 x 10 ¹² (P type doping)
Source/Drain Doping Concentration-1(S/D1)	0.06	1.06 x 10 ¹² (N type doping)
Source/Drain Doping Concentration-2(S/D2)	0.1	1.76 x 10 ¹² (N type doping)
Source/Drain Doping Concentration-3(S/D3)	0.3	5.28 x 10 ¹² (N type doping)

Other than doping concentration, gate oxide thickness for different oxide material is a tunable varying parameter, that we can change for better desirable performance of MOSFET. In this section we have analyzed the impact of different high-k oxide material (HfO₂& Al₂O₃) for different oxide layer thicknesses (4Å, 6Å, 8Å). Mathematically we can see that the gate capacitance is directly proportional to the quantum capacitance.

Figure 1. DOS of MOSFET with different doping concentrations of source-drain/channel
 a. (S/D-1, C1), b. (S/D-2, C-1), c. (S/D-3, C-1),
 m. (S/D-1, C-2), n. (S/D-2, C-2), o. (S/D-3, C-2),
 x. (S/D-1, C-3), y. (S/D-2, C-3), z. (S/D-3, C-3).

$$\therefore \frac{1}{C_g} = \frac{1}{C_{ox}} + \frac{1}{C_q} \quad (4)$$

$$\Rightarrow C_g = \frac{C_{ox} \cdot C_q}{C_{ox} + C_q} = \frac{C_q}{1 + \frac{C_q}{C_{ox}}} \quad (5)$$

As $C_{ox} \gg C_q$

$$\therefore C_g \approx C_q \quad (6)$$

But in the simulated DOS in **figure 2** we can see the with the change of gate capacitance the quantum capacitance is also changing, as the quantum capacitance can refer to as the density of available energy states near Fermi energy level. In **figure 2** we observed that, in case of Al_2O_3 for T_{ox} 6Å and 8Å the probability of tunneling is more as there are allowed energy states in the channel region. And in the case of HfO_2 for T_{ox} 4Å and 8Å the no. of available states is less so the amount of drain current will be less. So, for HfO_2 Oxide layer thickness of 6Å and for Al_2O_3 Oxide layer thickness of 4Å giving us the best result.

The absence of the allowed energy states in the energy window domain in MOSFET with air layer thickness 4Å **figure 3(a)** does not match our requirements. The MOSFET with air layer thickness of 6Å has a greater number of allowed energy states than that of the MOSFET with air layer thickness of 10Å. Again, the allowed energy states near the channel region are more in (c) compared to (b) so the probability of tunneling in (c) is more than in (b). So, the device with T_{air} 6Å is the best result.

Figure 2. DOS of MOSFET for various thickness of oxide layers (T_{ox}) of two high k material HfO_2 & Al_2O_3 a. for $HfO_2, T_{ox} = 4\text{Å}$ b. for $HfO_2, T_{ox} = 6\text{Å}$ c. for $HfO_2, T_{ox} = 8\text{Å}$ x. for $Al_2O_3, T_{ox} = 4\text{Å}$ y. for $Al_2O_3, T_{ox} = 6\text{Å}$ z. for $Al_2O_3, T_{ox} = 8\text{Å}$.

Moreover, we also simulated the DOS for varying thickness of air layer ($4\text{Å}, 6\text{Å}, 10\text{Å}$)(Figure 3).

Figure 3. DOS of MOSFET for various thickness of air layers (T_{air}) a. $T_{air} = 4\text{Å}$ b. $T_{air} = 6\text{Å}$ c. $T_{air} = 10\text{Å}$

But after simulation for the IV characteristics of the afore mentioned doping concentrations, we find that the device with the doping concentration (b) shows an ambipolar nature whereas the device with the doping concentration (a) shows the nature of an ideal MOSFET.

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{q} \int G(E)(f_1 - f_2) dE \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } G(E) = \frac{q^2}{h} \text{Trace}[\Gamma_1 G^R \Gamma_2 G^A]$$

$G(E)$ = Conductance as a function of Energy

f_1, f_2 = fermi function of 2 contacts

G^R = Retarded Green's Function
 G^A = Complex Conjugate Transpose of G^R
 Γ_1, Γ_2 = Energy spread in two Contacts

Figure 4. Drain current vs Gate-Source Voltage Characteristics of MOSFET with different doping concentrations of source-drain/channel S/D1, C1 & S/D2, C1.

The ambipolar nature will not provide any benefit as a CMOS device. Depending on the gate Voltage it can act both like an N-MOSFET and a P-MOSFET.

In figure 5 we have the results for the I_D vs V_{DS} characteristics of the MOSFET with the doping concentration S/D1, C1 for different gate voltages.

Figure 5. I_D vs V_{DS} Characteristics for MOSFET with doping Concentration S/D1, C1.

Figure 6. I_D vs V_{GS} characteristics for P-MOS and N-MOS

In figure 6 we can see that there is no major difference between the characteristics of N-MOSFET and P-MOSFET, where BP is used as the material.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In our work we got significant low OFF current as per IRDS roadmap⁷ recommendation but to achieve ON current we need to apply more gate voltage i.e. more than 1.5V the reason behind this is high Sub-threshold Slope (SS) that cannot be achieved below 100mV/dec. To improve SS two precautions can be adopted i.e. using the anisotropic nature of the material, of BP, we can go for selecting the transport direction to be zig-zag direction of the BP, where the effective mass is high. Another way to improve SS is to form a L shaped gate structure so that the transport direction is along arm-chair direction for ON condition and in the zig-zag direction for the OFF condition. By decreasing SS, we can attain a high ON-OFF ratio to fulfil the requirements of a low power (LP) device, as we have already accomplished the low off current, which was the primary issue in MOSFETs. Interestingly, we can see that BP's ambipolar behaviour, which has been documented in several articles, may be resolved simply by altering the doping concentration, as the figure already illustrates. Since BP has a higher mobility for holes than for electrons, it is said that BP material is suitable for P-MOSFET design. However, in our work, we found no significant difference between P-MOSFET and N-MOSFET for a given doping concentration.

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